

Europe's Warming Seas

Tackling the increasing risk of
marine heatwaves - and why
ocean warming data falls short

POLICY BRIEFING

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About ObsSea4Clim

<https://obssea4clim.eu/>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136548>

<https://zenodo.org/communities/obssea4clim>

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Highlights and Key Recommendations

Highlights

Climate change dramatically reshapes the ocean conditions, manifested by ocean warming that extends from surface to subsurface waters across all ocean basins. Key climate impact drivers include rising sea-level, marine heatwaves and changing weather patterns.

Marine heatwaves (MHWs) are becoming more frequent, intense, and long-lasting across European seas. They are only partially predictable, and highly disruptive to marine ecosystems, coastal communities, and ocean-based economies, requiring urgent integration into EU climate adaptation and marine policy frameworks. Scientifically, MHWs remain insufficiently understood and monitored, particularly when it comes to their subsurface manifestation and evolution.

Marine heatwaves contribute to:

- Mass mortality of marine species, including commercial species
- Fisheries and aquaculture losses
- Marine ecosystem degradation
- Human health risks associated with harmful algal blooms
- Changes in weather patterns and coastal climate
- Enhanced risk of risk of weather extremes

Strengthening scientific understanding, monitoring capacity, and early warning systems for MHWs will therefore be essential to support resilient marine management and informed climate policy across Europe.

Picture credit: Steffen M. Olsen, DMI

Policy Recommendations

- 1.** Establish a **scalable and standardised MHW indicator framework** for European seas, which is guided by the context of the impacts and ensures comparability and policy usability.
- 2.** Establish a **future-proof, sustainable, and resilient ocean observing system under the frameworks of Global Ocean Observing System** and the Ocean Act that fully addresses the ocean observation requirements for the early detection, monitoring, and warning of marine heatwaves across all European seas.
- 3.** The Subsurface Ocean Temperature Essential Ocean Variable **should be integrated in the Global Basic Observing Network (GBON)** as recommended by the Joint Collaborative board between WMO and IOC.
- 4.** **Ensure broad access to Ocean Best Practices** for monitoring and data management to support the required observational coverage, data quality, and data security.
- 5.** Support the **development of an integrated multipurpose observing system that takes optimal advantage of platforms and new technologies.** Such efforts are needed in order to deliver the suite of Essential Ocean Variables required for evaluation of multi stressors on the marine environment and ecosystem.
- 6.** **Invest in Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems and coupled ocean-atmosphere models** to improve seasonal and subsurface prediction skill and early warning for ecosystems in the coastal zone.

Context of the issue

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The EU Ocean Pact (COM/2025/281) adopted by the European Commission in June 2025 and the forthcoming EU Ocean Act (reference) establish a single coherent strategic framework bringing together all EU ocean-related policies under one overarching vision. It responds directly to the accelerating deterioration of ocean health driven by climate change, pollution and over-exploitation, while recognising the ocean's central role in Europe's climate resilience, food security, competitiveness and security.

A core innovation of the Ocean Pact is that it explicitly recognised ocean observation and marine knowledge as an essential public good for ecosystem protection, fisheries management, coastal adaptation and early warning for extreme events. The opening speech by President von der Leyen at the European Ocean Days further stressed that climate-driven extremes in the ocean must be anticipated rather than merely observed ex-post, requiring a step change in Europe's capacity to monitor, understand and predict ocean warming.

In this context, MHWs are emerging as one of the most visible and disruptive manifestations of ocean warming, yet they remain insufficiently understood and monitored.

As an example of ocean extremes, marine heatwaves are a systemic and growing climate risk for Europe. With improved forecasting, ecosystem-based management, and coordinated governance, their impacts can be substantially reduced, but only with proactive, integrated policy action. A critical enabling condition is the development of a strengthened and sustained ocean observing system, built on consistent, long-term, and interoperable data collection and analysis frameworks across European seas. Enhancing coordination through systems such as Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet and European observing networks will be essential to ensure reliable detection, prediction, and response to marine heatwaves.

This system should be built on standardised, interoperable, and quality-controlled observation and analysis protocols, combining satellite, in situ, and autonomous platform data streams. It should ensure continuous coverage, open data access, and harmonised indicators of marine heatwave intensity, duration, and frequency, enabling comparability across regions and time.

On one hand, sustained coordinated national and EU investments are essential to move toward a permanent climate service infrastructure, ensuring reliable early warning, trend detection, and impact attribution for marine heatwaves and supporting both adaptation planning and marine policy implementation.

At the same time, in the context of new European policy frameworks, there is a clear opportunity to elevate ocean warming and MHW monitoring from a scientific concern to a key policy priority to support addressing the challenges highlighted by the Ocean Pact as well as and the forthcoming EU Ocean Act.

Likewise, initiatives such as Ocean Eye, can play a pivotal role by integrating satellite and subsurface ocean observations, and enabling continuous, high-resolution tracking of ocean heat content.

Our Evidence and Analysis

Evidence and analysis

Defined as prolonged periods of abnormally high sea surface temperatures locally or across larger regions, MHWs can persist from days to months, causing harmful algal blooms, mass mortality of fish, corals, and other species, shifting species distributions, and threatening fisheries and aquaculture systems that coastal communities depend on. MHWs can modulate local atmospheric conditions and exacerbate heat extremes, droughts and rainfall over land. As climate change accelerates, these events are becoming more frequent, more intense, and more widespread, transforming them from episodic anomalies into a systemic risk for Europe's marine environment and blue economy. They are predicted to be key features of the marine climate of the North Atlantic and Arctic Ocean within a few decades, coupled with climate and weather extremes and abrupt sea ice retreat (ESOTC 2025).

Globally, marine heatwaves have more than doubled in frequency since the 1980s (Oliver et al. 2018). The Mediterranean Sea is a recurring hotspot, experiencing repeated marine heatwaves (2003, 2015, 2018, 2022 and 2025; McAdam et al. 2024; Darmaraki et al. 2024) that have contributed to biodiversity loss and stress on fisheries (Garrobou et al. 2022). The Baltic Sea has also experienced multiple heatwaves; coinciding with low oxygen levels, and the heatwaves amplify the ecological risks in this already vulnerable ecosystem (Safonova et al. 2024). In the North Atlantic and Subpolar region, MHWs are nested with long-term climate forcings, ocean warming and stratification changes, reflecting an acceleration of ocean warming.

The key challenge in observing and predicting MHWs and their features under continued climate change lies in their complexity. MHWs are driven by interactions between oceanic and atmospheric processes (Darmaraki et al. 2024, Denaxa et al. 2024, Bonino & McAdam et al. 2025), varying significantly across regions and timescales. Critically, much of their evolution occurs below the surface (Capotondi et al. 2025), where current observing capacities remain sparse and less accessible from satellite observing systems. This limits our ability to detect early warning signals, understand subsurface heat accumulation, and anticipate coupled biogeochemical changes, such as oxygen levels, and consequently ecosystem impacts.

Figure 1. Framework for defining MHWs. Source: <https://www.marineheatwaves.org/mhw-overview.html>.

ObsSea4Clim contributions

The EU project ObsSea4Clim has advanced understanding of the drivers, monitoring, and predictability of marine heatwaves (MHWs) in European seas. Our recent results further highlight the importance of improving both observing systems and forecasting capabilities to strengthen climate resilience and early-warning capacity.

Research within ObsSea4Clim identified large-scale atmospheric weather patterns that trigger marine heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea (Bonino & McAdam, 2025). Improved representation of these atmosphere–ocean interactions in Earth System Models (ESMs) and operational forecasting systems is essential to enhance predictive skill and support the development of effective early-warning and mitigation strategies in the Mediterranean basin.

Subsurface monitoring of MHWs in European seas currently relies heavily on the use of ocean data reanalyses (Lima et al. 2026). However, the accuracy of these products remains constrained by insufficient in situ observations. More consistent and sustained multi-platform ocean observing systems are therefore required both to improve the representation of ocean conditions in reanalyses and to expand the availability of validation data.

In parallel, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Rolling Review of Requirements is being applied to MHWs to assess current observing capacity and identify technology-independent observational requirements. Limited availability of consistent temperature readings at depths remains a major limitation, as it restricts the ability to characterise subsurface MHWs and their evolution. Existing observing infrastructure, such as fixed moorings, remains sparse, unevenly distributed, and often too short in duration to robustly define extremes relative to local climatological conditions (see figure below).

Figure 2. Copernicus Marine in-situ moorings in the Mediterranean Sea. Left: all 187 moorings. Right: 27 moorings with >20 years of data, which is sufficient to define climatological threshold for extremes.

ObsSea4Clim has also contributed to the development of user-relevant marine heatwave information products, including a marine heatwave atlas for ocean surface conditions (project hackathon output; Hayward et al., in review). Such products can support marine management, climate adaptation planning, and improved communication of marine heatwave risks to policymakers and stakeholders.

References

About ObsSea4Clim

The results emerging from ObsSea4Clim are available on the Zenodo platform:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/obssea4clim>

Website: <https://www.obssea4clim.eu>

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